

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE X

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

October 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), p.111, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

QUICK REQUEST: A KIOSK-BASED SYSTEM FOR THE REGISTRAR OFFICE OF UNIVERSIDAD DE MANILA

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Abstract

The Universidad de Manila's rising need for academic document requests has shown challenges such as long lines, delays and miscommunication. The study developed the Quick Request, a kiosk-based solution that aims to automate and simplify registrar processes in order to solve these problems. The study aimed to enhance the speed, accuracy, and transparency of document requests by providing an automated system through which users can request documents, track status and collect their documents without having to wait in long queues while also improving the user experience for both student, alumni and registrar staff. It is a system consisting of Quick Response (QR) code integration with reference number, which can check the real-time status, email notification once the request document is done, and the dashboard for the administration to better manage requests. The system was designed, tested and evaluated iteratively with user feedback using PHP, MySQL and Codeigniter 4 as part of the Agile process.

The evaluation used the ISO/IEC 25010 quality model, conducting an analysis of seven important attributes, namely, Functionality, Performance Efficiency, Usability, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, and Portability. The scores obtained showed very high levels in Functionality (4.6), Usability (4.6), Reliability (4.8), and Security (4.8), which means that the system can fulfill its purported tasks, provide an easy-to-use interface, and ensure the safety of information. Performance Efficiency (4.4) and Maintainability (4.4) rated above average with a possibility of improvement under heavy loads and when operating over long durations. Portability was rated as moderately as 3.8 which shows that more compatibility with various operating systems needs to be widened. In summary, the results showed that by lowering errors, cutting down on waiting times and improving service transparency, the kiosk-based system offers a notable improvement over the conventional manual process.

The study concludes that the Quick Request is much more effective in optimizing the document request process, lessening the queue, improving transparency, and boosting student and alumni satisfaction. It also enables efficiency on the part of registrar staff in processing requests, resulting in improved productivity. The proponents recommend future enhancement that include mobile and web-based access, multifactor authentication to provide extra protection to data, and adding cloud storage and analytics to improve scalability and to meet the needs that are changing over time within the institution. This study outlines potential advantages of kiosk-based automation of improving the efficiency of public services and the experience of users within higher education institutions.

Keywords: Quick Request, kiosk-based system, registrar office, document request, Quick Response (QR) code

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17349816

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